

Optimized Kalman Filter for External Force Estimation Using Deep Reinforcement Learning

Hossein Barati¹, Young Jin Park^{1*}

¹ Department of Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering, Gyeongsang National University, Jinju, 52828, Korea (hosseinbarati39@gmail.com, youngjin.park@gnu.ac.kr) * Corresponding author

Abstract: Accurate external force estimation is essential in robotic systems, and the Kalman Filter is a widely used method for this purpose. However, the filter's performance heavily depends on properly tuned noise covariances, which are often set manually through trial and error. In this work, a deep reinforcement learning approach based on Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) is used to automatically optimize the Kalman Filter's parameters. The learning agent interacts with a custom environment, adjusting the noise covariances to minimize the estimation error of joint velocity. Compared to conventional manual tuning, the PPO-optimized filter yields smoother and more accurate estimations. The results demonstrate the potential of reinforcement learning for adaptive Kalman Filter tuning in dynamic systems.

Keywords: force estimation, Kalman Filter, reinforcement learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate estimation of external forces is essential in robotic and control systems, especially when direct force sensors are unavailable or impractical. A widely used approach for indirect force estimation is Kalman Filter-based estimation, which provides an optimal state estimation framework for linear systems affected by stochastic noise [1]. By modeling system dynamics and incorporating noisy measurements, the Kalman Filter can estimate unmeasurable states such as external forces, improving control performance and system awareness [2]. In this study, a discrete-time Kalman Filter was applied to estimate external torque in a single motor system. Previous studies have demonstrated Kalman filtering for force estimation. For example, both the external torque and the actuating torque were estimated simultaneously using a discrete Kalman Filter with manually tuned process noise and measurement noise [3].

However, these approaches often rely on manual tuning of the noise covariances Q and R , which is time-consuming and sensitive to system changes. To address this, we propose a novel method that uses deep reinforcement learning (RL)—specifically the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm—to automatically tune Q and R . The agent interacts with a Kalman filtering environment, receives performance-based rewards, and learns to minimize velocity estimation error, enabling adaptive and accurate parameter tuning.

2. Method

2.1 Autonomous System Model

To estimate external forces in a single motor system without a gearbox, the system is modeled by the dynamic equations:

$$J_\theta \ddot{\theta}(t) + B_\theta \dot{\theta}(t) = \tau_{tot}(t) \quad (1)$$

Here, $\theta(t)$ is the joint angle, J_θ the moment of inertia, and B_θ is the viscous damping coefficient. The total torque includes both commanded and external torque, i.e.,

$$\tau_{tot}(t) = \tau_{cmd}(t) + \tau_{ext}(t) \quad (2)$$

From (2), the external torque is then obtained if the commanded torque is available.

We define the state vector as

$$x(t) = [\theta(t) \quad \dot{\theta}(t) \quad \tau_{tot}(t)]^T \quad (3)$$

To adopt an autonomous model, the total resultant torque $\tau_{tot}(t)$ is treated as an unmeasured input with random-walk dynamics [3] so that the continuous-time state-space model is given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bw(t), \quad (4)$$

$$y(t) = Cx(t) + v(t). \quad (5)$$

with system matrices:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{B_\theta}{J_\theta} & \frac{1}{J_\theta} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, C = [1 \quad 0 \quad 0] \quad (6)$$

where $w(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q)$, $v(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R)$ representing the process and measurement noise, respectively. The system is then discretized with a sampling time Δt as:

$$x_{k+1} = Fx_k + Gw_k, \quad (7)$$

$$z_k = Hx_k + v_k. \quad (8)$$

where F, G, H are the discrete equivalents of A, B, C , respectively [4]. Finally, the Kalman Filter is employed to recursively estimate the system states $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$

2.2 Parameter Tuning via Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

Manually tuning the noise covariances Q and R in Kalman filtering is often suboptimal and labor-intensive, especially in systems with nonlinear or varying dynamics. To address this, we employ a deep RL approach using the PPO algorithm [5] to automatically determine optimal Q and R values that minimize estimation error. We formulated the problem as an RL task, where the agent selects log-scaled actions $\log_{10}(Q)$ and $\log_{10}(R)$. For each training episode, the Kalman filter runs on the same pre-recorded motor-encoder data that serve as the Kalman Filter observation. Estimation performance is evaluated by comparing estimated angular velocity $\hat{\theta}$ with the ground-truth θ_{gnd} , obtained via numerical differentiation followed by zero-phase low-pass filtering. Because direct external force measurements were unavailable, velocity data were used as a reliable alternative for reward calculation.

Estimation accuracy is quantified by the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (\hat{\theta}_k - \theta_{gnd,k})^2} \quad (9)$$

The reward function is defined as:

$$r = -\log_{10}(RMSE + 10^{-12}) - Penalty_{bounds} \quad (10)$$

where the constant prevents singularities, and the penalty discourages boundary actions.

The agent's observations include error statistics (mean, standard deviation, extrema), RMSE, and the last selected $\log_{10}(Q)$ and $\log_{10}(R)$ values. Training used a multilayer perceptron policy, with actor and critic networks each comprising two hidden layers (64 and 32 units, ReLU activations). After 100000 time steps, the agent successfully learned to minimize estimation error. The final implementation was done using the Stable-Baselines3 library [6], and the best-performing Q and R were applied in the Kalman Filter for evaluation.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed framework.

3. Results

The proposed PPO-based Kalman Filter tuning was evaluated against manually selected noise covariances. As shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the PPO-optimized estimation is significantly smoother. The optimized values obtained via reinforcement learning were $Q = 3.53 \times 10^{-2}$ and $R = 1.42 \times 10^{-7}$, while the manually set values were $Q = 9.5 \times 10^{-5}$ and $R = 1.0 \times 10^{-10}$.

These results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method through automatic Kalman Filter tuning.

Fig. 2. Simulation Results with PPO-optimized Q & R : (a) motor velocity, (b) external torque.

Fig. 3. Simulation Results with Manually Tuned Q & R : (a) motor velocity, (b) external torque.

4. CONCLUSION

This study presented a reinforcement learning-based method for optimizing Kalman Filter parameters to improve external force estimation in a single motor system. Using the PPO algorithm, the approach replaces manual tuning by learning noise covariances Q and R . The resulting Kalman Filter produced smoother and more accurate velocity estimates than manually tuned filters. These results highlight the potential of reinforcement learning as a data-driven solution for adaptive filtering in dynamic environments.

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